

Thioketonic Esters. Part III. Alkylation of Ethyl Thioacetoacetate.

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Ethyl thioacetoacetate was suitably alkylated by the action of alkyl halides on its sodium derivative obtained by the action of the ester over metallic sodium in benzene suspension. The following derivatives were prepared by the action of the corresponding halides on the sodium derivative of ethyl thioacetoacetate:

Ethyl β -ethylmercaptocrotonate (b.p. 114-17°/15 mm.)

Ethyl β -*n*-propylmercaptocrotonate (b.p. 117-20°/15 mm.)

Ethyl β -*n*-amylmercaptocrotonate (126-28°/15 mm.)

Ethyl β -benzylmercaptocrotonate (m.p. 68, b. p. 155-60°/15mm.)

Ethyl β -(benzoylmethyl)-mercaptocrotonate (m.p. 85°).

On treatment with phenylhydrazine, these compounds do not give sulphuretted hydrogen under ordinary conditions, thus showing the absence of a free thioketonic group in them. On treatment with phenylhydrazine at its boiling point, however, they evolve mercaptans and a considerable quantity of dehydropyrazolone is obtained. The reaction can evidently be represented as follows:—

This constitution of the ethers was further supported by the fact that it decolourised bromine water. They did not give any lead salt thus showing the absence of a free thiol group in them. In the formation of *S*-ethers, ethyl thioacetate differs from ethyl acetoacetate which forms mainly *C*-derivatives under ordinary conditions. The action of reducing agents gave rise to mercaptans, thus showing that the alkyl groups are linked to the sulphur atom.

On boiling these compounds with dilute acids, the degradation products were found to be acetone and the corresponding mercaptans. The reaction seems to take place as follows:—

The behaviour of ethyl β -thiodicrotonate towards alcoholic potash (*cf. J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 71) in conjunction with the results obtained by boiling the alkylated products with dilute acids leads us to conclude that although these alkyl derivatives of the esters are similar in structure to alkyl sulphide, they differ from the latter in being more sensitive to chemical reagents than the alkyl sulphides. Evidently the sulphur atom is under some influence to which this increased labile nature can be attributed.

These alkyl derivatives are found to distil under reduced pressure through a long range of temperature, but analytical data of the lowest and the highest boiling fractions were found to be identical. This may be ascribed to the presence of geometrical isomers of the products. This inference was found to be correct on an examination of the acid obtained by careful hydrolysis of the ethyl derivative by means of alcoholic potash. This acid was found to melt at 86° whereas its *cis*- and *trans*-forms, (obtained by the action of the sodium salt of ethyl mercaptans on *cis*- and *trans*-chlorocrotonic acids (*Annalen*, 1889, **254**, 234; *Ber.*, 1899, **32**, 2806) melt at 112° and 92° respectively. The acid was probably a mixture of these two isomers.

The following acids were obtained under identical conditions: (1) β -Ethylmercaptocrotonic acid (m.p. 85°). (2) β -*n*-Propylmercaptocrotonic acid (m.p. 70°). (3) β -Benzylmercaptocrotonic acid (m.p. 134°).

The free acid from ethyl β -thiodicrotonate could not be isolated under similar conditions (cf. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 71. This compound is evidently more sensitive to part with sulphur than the alkyl derivatives mentioned above.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl β -ethylmercaptocrotonate.—Ethyl thioacetoacetate (30 g.), diluted with benzene, was treated with metallic sodium (5 g.) in benzene suspension. During the treatment (3 hours) the reaction flask was cooled in ice-water with constant shaking and the whole was kept for 2 hours. Ethyl iodide (34 g.) was added to sodium derivative of the ester and the whole was refluxed on a water-bath for 7 hours. The product was then extracted with benzene; the extract after drying over calcium chloride was made free from benzene and subjected to vacuum distillation. The fractions between (i) 72° - 73° (ii) 73° - 114° and (iii) 114° - 117° under 15 mm. pressure were collected. [Found: (i) C, 55.02; H, 8.57; S, 18; (iii) C, 55.0; H, 8.1; S, 18.02; M.W., 170.2. $C_8H_{14}O_2S$ requires C, 55.1; H, 8.1; S, 18.36 per cent; M.W., 174).

*Ethyl β -*n*-propylmercaptocrotonate.*—Ethyl thioacetoacetate (30g.) was treated with sodium (5 g.) as before and the sodium derivative was then refluxed with *n*-propyl iodide (38 g.) on a water-bath for 7 hours. The product was then isolated as in the previous case and distilled in vacuum. The fraction between 117° - $120^\circ/15$ mm. was collected. (Found: C, 56.7; H, 9.4; S, 16.71; M.W., 189.9. $C_9H_{16}O_2S$ requires C, 57.4; H, 9.0; S, 17.0 per cent; M.W., 188).

*Ethyl β -*n*-amylmercaptocrotonate.*—Ethyl thioacetoacetate (30g.) was treated with sodium (5g.) as before and the product was refluxed with *n*-amyl iodide on a water-bath for 7 hours. On distillation under 15 mm. pressure, the fraction between 126 - 28° was collected. (Found: S, 14.58. $C_{11}H_{20}O_2S$ requires S, 14.82 per cent).

Ethyl β -benzylmercaptocrotonate.—The sodium derivative obtained from ethyl thioacetoacetate (30g.) and sodium (5g.) was refluxed with

benzyl chloride (34g.) on a water-bath for 12 hours. The product was isolated as usual and distilled under 15 mm. pressure. The fraction between 155°-160° was collected and found to solidify after 2 or 3 days, m.p. 68°. (Found: S, 13.45. $C_{13}H_{16}O_2S$ requires S, 13.56 per cent).

Ethyl β -(benzoylmethyl)-mercaptocrotonate.— The sodium derivative prepared as before was refluxed with benzene solution of ω -bromoacetophenone (41g.) on a water-bath for 12 hours. The impure liquid product was solidified with freezing mixture and the solid product was isolated by rapid filtration and finally crystallised from ethyl alcohol, m.p. 85°. (Found: S, 12.06. $C_{14}H_{16}O_3S$ requires S, 12.13 per cent).

General properties of the alkylated products.— The alkylated products do neither form lead salts nor give any coloration with ferric chloride. With phenylhydrazine, they give no reaction at the ordinary temperature; but on heating the mixture on sand-bath, the mercaptans are given off which can be detected with lead acetate paper and from the reaction mixture, a considerable quantity of dehydropyrazolone is obtained. They decolourise bromine water immediately and have no constant boiling point. When they are subjected to reducing action, the mercaptans are given off, and on boiling with dilute mineral acids the mercaptans with carbon dioxide are evolved. They can generally be hydrolysed with alcoholic potash at the ordinary temperature to the corresponding β -alkylmercaptocrotonic acids.

Action of Phenylhydrazine on Alkylated Products.

On n-propyl derivative.—Ethyl β -n-propylmercaptocrotonate (3g.) was heated with phenylhydrazine (3g.) on sand-bath with an air-condenser for a few hours. When tested with lead acetate paper, a mercaptan was found to evolve, frequently accompanied by H_2S gas, due perhaps to the decomposition of mercaptan at high temperatures. After completion of the reaction, the products were washed with ether and crystallised from pyridine, m.p. 330° (decomp.). (Found: N, 16.89. dehydropyrazolone requires N, 17.0 per cent).

On benzyl derivative.—Equimolecular quantities of ethyl β -benzylmercaptocrotonate and phenylhydrazine were heated on sand-bath, when H_2S gas was evolved. On completion of the reaction, the residue gave out smell similar to that of dibenzyl sulphide and it was then washed with acetone. A product was obtained melting at 330° (decomp.) (dehydropyrazolone, m.p. 330°),

Action of dilute mineral acids on ethyl β -ethylmercaptocrotonate.—Ethyl β -ethylmercaptocrotonate (15g.) was heated with 10% H_2SO_4 (200 c.c.) on wire gauze under reflux. The escaping gases were passed successively through ethyl alcohol and a solution of barium hydroxide. The heating was continued till carbon dioxide ceased to evolve. Acetone was detected in the aqueous solution by the usual colour reactions.

The alcohol, over which the escaping gases were passed, was treated with alcoholic solution of iodine till the colour of iodine did not vanish. The resulting product was extracted with ether and washed with sodium thiosulphate solution to remove excess of iodine. After evaporating off the ether, it boiled at 152° and was found to be diethyl disulphide (b.p. 152°).

Action of Alcoholic Potash on Alkylated Products.

β -Ethylmercaptocrotonic acid.—Ethyl β -ethylmercaptocrotonate (1 mol.) was kept with 12% alcoholic potash (1 mol.) over-night. The mixture was then diluted with ice-water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitated product was filtered and crystallised from methyl alcohol and the crystals were washed with petroleum ether, m. p. 86° . (Found: S, 21.46. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires S, 21.92 per cent).

β -n-Propylmercaptocrotonic acid.—Ethyl β -n-propylmercaptocrotonate (1 mol.) was treated as above with one mol. of alcoholic potash. The solid product was crystallised from methyl alcohol and washed with petroleum ether, mp. 70° . (Found: S, 19.74. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires S, 20.0 per cent).

β -Benzylmercaptocrotonic acid.—Ethyl β -benzylmercaptocrotonate was treated as before with alcoholic potash. The acid obtained was crystallised from ethyl alcohol and the crystals were washed with petroleum ether, m.p. 134° . (Found: S, 15.54. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires S, 15.88 per cent).

Reduction of ethyl β -ethylmercaptocrotonate.—Ethyl β -ethylmercaptocrotonate (15g.) was subjected to the reducing action of zinc-amalgam and dilute hydrochloric acid and kept over-night. A mercaptan was found to evolve when tested with lead acetate paper. On completion of the reaction, the product was extracted with ether. The product was found to contain no sulphur and had boiling point 92° ; it was probably ethyl propionate (b.p. 98°).

